

IoT for experimentation in control systems education

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Abstract

Engineering education and control systems education face the challenge of updating their curricular elements to adapt to the new needs of industry and society. New technical and transversal competencies, related to technological change, such as the use of digital tools like the Internet of Things IoT, and computer knowledge, are reported as required in the industry. The work presents tools for experimentation in control systems, using cloud computing, IoT, digital communications, and data analysis. Any student with Internet connectivity, programs the controllers in the cloud, anytime, anywhere; using inexpensive rapid prototyping systems such as Raspberry Pi, and low-cost IoT devices, they perform experiments on real systems such as air temperature, soil humidity, and the level of a water tank. Experiences of using these technologies are presented in an interdisciplinary control course, and the first engineering project course, from the electronic engineering program of the Universidad del Valle. Both courses use Project Based Learning, enhanced using these new technologies.

Keywords: Engineering Education; Internet of Things, Control Systems, Digital Communications.

1 Introduction

Technological change has generated a gap between industry and academia (Besová & Tupa, 2007). Multiple works have reported the integration of new technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Cloud Computing, Internet of Things (IoT), and Data Analysis, in the industry (Xu, Xu & Li, 2018). The industry now requires engineers with specific competencies such as knowledge and use of the aforementioned technologies, and transversal competencies such as computational literacy, problem-solving, teamwork, and others (Kumar & Ekren, 2020).

The focus of Convergent Technologies and Industries 4.0 of the Wise Mission (Minciencias, 2020), from the description of Critical Architecture for Innovation and Global Opportunity, proposes in the Foundational Layer, elements such as cloud computing, affordable high-speed communication, and cybersecurity; in the Value Layer, IoT, data analysis, robotics, and sensors. Additionally, this Mission in the focus of Social Sciences and Human Development with Equity proposes as the first strategic axis of intervention, the reduction of educational gaps and those that affect access to science and technology, to contribute to sociocultural equity, and economic growth. The different types of technologies of Industry 4.0 are from various disciplines, so there is the need to have learning environments where they can be integrated, with their respective support resources, and with active learning methodologies that facilitate the development of transversal skills for their use, design, and technological programming, (Universia, 2024).

This paper presents support resources for learning activities in two engineering courses. The first course is an integrative project course in the sixth semester of the electronic engineering program; the course integrates project management tools with the disciplines of control systems and communications. It uses as an experimentation tool a digital control system with a radio frequency communication network. The second is an elective course interdisciplinary, offered to electrical, mechanical, chemical, and electronic engineering. It uses an IoT experimentation platform, which allows Ethernet networked control systems and the controller in the cloud.

The rest of this document is structured as follows: section 2 presents the courses of Engineering Projects, System Controls, and Communications. Section 3 shows the different schemes of the experimental prototypes for integrated control and communication experimentation. Some experimental results and students' opinions about the resources are presented in section 4. Finally, section 5 presents conclusions and future work.

2 Projects, controls, and communications courses

IoT enables the interconnectivity of devices and systems, collecting and sharing data. Modern engineers must face increasingly complex, interconnected systems, applied in multiple fields of knowledge. Therefore, education in control systems and communications must provide a solid theoretical base, exploiting these new technologies. Furthermore, solutions to problems in engineering are normally carried out through projects, so it is also important to develop the transversal skills required for these projects. In response to these challenges in 2018 the Faculty of Engineering of the Universidad del Valle carried out a curricular reform of its 18 undergraduate programs (González, 2019). The curricular redesign established, for all the faculty's programs, engineering project courses in the upper semesters, to integrate the transversal skills and the necessary knowledge of various disciplines, to develop engineering projects, in disciplinary or interdisciplinary teams, that seek to solve problems in the engineering context.

Figure 1 shows the integration of projects, control, and communications courses for the electronics engineering program.

Figure 1. Project, control, and communications curricular components.

2.1 Engineering project courses

The engineering project courses are between the sixth and eighth semesters and have around 15 students. The courses are developed around integrative projects whose milestone is the analysis of a contextual problem and the conception and execution of a project that allows its solution, integrating different concepts of electronic engineering. Throughout these courses, financial analysis tools and project management skills are addressed, and the transversal competencies: Capacity to develop engineering projects, teamwork, and communication skills, engineering problem-solving skills, critical, creative and systemic thinking. Teams of three students address the different phases of the project, where they define the problem and design a solution, which is implemented in an emulation prototype. Experimental practical training is carried out with the activities demanded in the project. Evaluation activities are training reports, written reports, and oral presentations to the entire group about the progress of each project.

The first engineering project course has learning outcomes to perform the conceptual analysis and basic engineering, as well as design and implement a PID control system, with a wireless communication network. In

the Engineering Project II course, students perform detailed engineering for more complex systems that require other controllers like RST and state feedback, use electronic instrumentation for measurement, and communication networks with Ethernet. The third course integrates disciplines of high-level industrial automation, wide area networks, artificial intelligence, and environmental impacts of solutions.

To learn project skills in the Engineering Project I course, master classes, role plays, and training in software tools for project management are carried out. The course integrates the control and communication disciplines, through contextualized projects, whose solutions are implemented in a laboratory prototype. For example, the Irrigation Tank Project raises the problem: *'A sugar factory has an automatic irrigation system for a sugar cane growing area in the Cauca Valley, located in the foothills of the central mountain range. To feed this irrigation system, the sugar factory has a vertical cylindrical water tank with a 4m radius and one million liters of capacity, located 500m away and on a base 10m higher than the crop. The factory requires that a smart agriculture company with IoT (students) provide a system that prevents water spills in the tank and guarantees constant pressure to the irrigation system. The regional environmental authority CVC ensures that the communities and companies that use and exploit the water from the tributary to the tank, use it properly under the permits granted.'* The project is emulated in the Automatica Laboratory, using the PCT-M Water Tank Prototype, which has a tank, and a pump to change the inlet water flow and tank discharge pipes. In this course the initiation and planning phases of the project are addressed, defining the problem and performing the basic engineering to design a solution, which is implemented in the emulation prototype, using the experimental integrator resource for communication and control presented in the section 3. Experimental practical training is carried out with the activities demanded in the project, in another prototype for the speed control of a motor.

2.2 Control systems courses

Control systems in the IoT framework facilitate remote monitoring and control and improve performance through data analysis. The implementation of control laws could be digitally in micro-processed embedded systems or directly in cloud computing. Likewise, the high availability of online data requires data engineering to obtain discrete dynamic models and tune digital controllers.

In the two control courses, students can model, analyze, and design invariant, continuous, or discrete linear control systems with input-output and state space representation, in the temporal and frequency domain. In the control fundamentals course, students are expected to be able to: define the control system problem, model, and analyze feedback dynamic systems, and analyze PID control actions. In the analysis and control design course, students are expected to be able to: analyze the stability, the root locus, and the frequency response, and design PID, RST, state feedback controllers, and other control architectures. Control systems require high mathematical abstraction, with the use of mathematical concepts and tools for modeling, analysis, and design of dynamic systems. In the control courses, theoretical concepts are introduced through gamification, with animated games on the computer. The mathematical modeling, analysis, and design are carried out in computer rooms with the MATLAB® software (Matlab, 2024a), structured in computer books with live scripts (Matlab, 2024b). The application of the theory is carried out in theoretical-practical sessions in which portable and virtual laboratories are used in the classroom to bring the student closer to the theoretical concepts and the reality of the behavior of control systems.

The Interdisciplinary Control course is an elective offered to electrical, electronic, mechanical, and chemical engineering programs. In this course, data management techniques, data modeling, and design of discrete controllers are introduced, which allow for achieving maximum productivity and profit, and minimum energy consumption, in industrial and IoT environments. At the end of the course, is expected that the students will be able to define the characteristics and specifications for a control problem based on data; manage data for collection, processing, analysis, and display; model dynamic systems in discrete time from data; design PID,

RST, state feedback and predictive control laws based on models, to obtain the desired performance for the controlled system; integrate plant, measurement, actuation and communication with the discrete controller, to implement the designed control in an industrial and IoT environment. Students were organized into teams of three students, two of them from different disciplines. The projects were open to choose by the teams, which chose: The purification of water through a chlorine dosing plant, with industrial IoT; humidity control for a crop in the context of smart agriculture with IoT; level control of a water tank for a rural home, with IoT; and temperature control in a pipe through which a sugar solution flows, in the context of industrial IoT.

2.3 Communication courses

As shown in Figure 1, the communications curricular component is based on three theoretical courses: Communication Systems, Communication Networks I, and Communication Networks II. Although these courses are, in principle, theoretical in these days of great technological advances and digital competency, these courses are taught using a variety of tools such as simulators, mathematical animations, demonstrations in class using physical equipment such as routers, and so on. These courses at the same time contribute to the Engineering Project sequence (Figure 1). Learning activities for Engineering Project I include the programming and deployment of wireless devices mainly in point-to-point topologies. Learning activities for Engineering Project II include the programming of a simple LAN network applying concepts such as IP addressing, DHCP server, Gateway, VLAN, etc. Learning activities for Engineering Project III from the communications component include programming and implementation of WAN networks applying concepts such as inter-domain (e.g. BGP) and intra-domain (e.g., OSPF) routing protocols, MPLS, VRF, QoS, and so on.

The Communication Systems course is about the theory of the physical transmission of signals, a highly mathematical issue that addresses signals and transmission media in communication systems, communications link budget, random communication signals, reliable transmission of information, continuous wave modulation, and digital modulation. The first Communication Networks courses cover the classical content through the different layers of OSI, TCP/IP, and NGN communication network models that make the provision of services and applications through a data network, with the most visible example of this field of knowledge being the Internet. Communication Networks I encompass communication networks models, physical layer, and data link layer with all its underlying details. Communication Networks II encompasses the Network Layer, Transport Layer, Transport Layer Security, and Application Layer, it includes Network protocols in the context of LAN, MAN, and WAN networks; inter-domain and intra-domain routing protocols using distance vector, link state, and path vector (BGP) algorithms; medium-sized communication networks focused on solving data communication needs in corporate environments; and transport layer protocols, DHCP and DNS.

3 Experimental resources

Figure 2 shows the schema for integrated control and communication experimentation. The schema proposes different approaches to connect the controller and the process. Both the controller and the process can be deployed either locally or online where the process can be physical laboratory equipment or a virtual application.

Figure 2. General schema.

Table 1 summarises the different configurations proposed in the schema of Figure 2. The case where the controller is deployed locally and the nature of the process is physical corresponds to the traditional configuration of a laboratory at universities where practicing activities are performed using data acquisition boards and students have direct access to the laboratory equipment.

Table 1. Configurations of experimentation resources depend on the nature of the process, the type of connection between the process and the controller, and where the controller is deployed.

Controller	Nature of the process		Type of connection	
	Physical	Virtual	Local	Internet
Local	X		X	
		X	X	
		X		X
Online	X			X
		X		X

With the controller placed locally and the process online, the numerical dynamics of the process, which can be a tank-level, a thermic system, or any other, is deployed on the internet as an application. The application receives an input signal and generates an output signal that is sent back to the controller. The controller is implemented locally in MATLAB Simulink. Both elements communicate with each other using the TCP/IP protocol. MATLAB Simulink is equipped with TCP/IP connection blocks which makes it easy to configure and deploy control loops with multiple types of control algorithms like Proportional-Integral-Derivative and State Feedback. Table 1 also shows that with a local controller and a virtual process, the type of connection can be local. In the latter case, the application of the virtual process is hosted on a platform such as Raspberry Pi.

The connection mechanism implemented in the schema of Figure 2 introduces non-deterministic communication delays. The schema of Figure 2 assumes a sampling time that should be synchronized in both elements, controller, and process. The sampling time is selected according to the temporal response of the process and the performance requirements in a closed loop; also, communication latency must be considered to decrease the effect of connection delays.

For quasi-real-time execution on MATLAB Simulink, a sample time of 300 ms has been found as appropriate to synchronize controller computations and TCP/IP communications, the latter with communications through the internet. Working on a local wired network connection, communications, and controller computations can be synchronized with a sample time of 50 ms.

For local connections, a wired or wireless network can be used. Wired connections have been found more stable than wireless ones where data between consecutive samples can be lost. Wi-Fi and Radio Frequency RF communication technologies have been proposed to deploy the wireless approach. Using Wi-Fi, by the side of the controller, an application implementing a control algorithm capable of receiving the error signal and calculating the control signal; MATLAB Simulink along with the MyDAQ data acquisition board, and TCP/IP connection blocks, are used to acquire and generate the process and reference signals to finally calculate the error and send it to the controller.

Figure 3. Control loop using RF communication.

The use of RF communication requires extra hardware on both elements of the schema since RF devices cannot be connected directly to the computers. Figure 3 presents the elements disposed to use RF to communicate the process and the controller. The communication module of Figure 3 corresponds to an RF device of reference nRF24L01 plus a USB serial adapter. The USB adapter interfaces the RF device to a serial port which can be directly accessed from MATLAB Simulink.

To access the controller or the process deployed on the internet, public IP addresses of the applications running online should be available. There exist multiple services which provide solutions to deploy such applications. Additionally, tools like Ngrok (ngrok, 2024) allow to deployment of these applications online with no need for the cloud. Activities performed in control systems courses used Ngrok to deploy processes online and create cloud-based control loops to test control algorithms and do identification exercises.

The Interdisciplinary Control course used the scheme in Figure 2 with a local Raspberry Pi to emulate the process model, a local PC or in the cloud, was used for the controller. In the Engineering Project I course, the scheme in Figure 3 is used.

4 Results

This section presents some experimental results and students' opinions about the resources described in the last section.

4.1 Experimental results

Figure 4 shows the input-output response of a process deployed virtually through the internet. For this response, the configuration of the resources corresponds to a controller deployed locally on MATLAB Simulink, and the process is deployed virtually using a Raspberry Pi board, and communication through the internet with the tool Ngrok. In Figure 4 the control system is in an open loop and the controller is reduced to a unitary gain. As can be seen in Figure 4, the response features communication delays which are visible with input changes.

Figure 4. Input-output response. Process deployed virtually through the internet.

In Figure 5, the input-output response corresponds to a temperature control with a RST controller deployed in the cloud and the process is a pipe through which a sugar solution flows, deployed virtually in a Raspberry Pi board. Good performance is observed in tracking the reference and rejecting the disturbance between 40 and 60 s.

Figure 5. Input-output response. Process deployed virtually through the internet.

In Figure 6, the input-output response corresponds to a local controller connected to physical laboratory equipment using RF communication. In this configuration, the physical system used was a direct current motor and the signal sensed was the angular speed interfaced to the data acquisition board using a tachometer which finally provides a voltage signal.

Figure 6. Input-output response. Local controller and physical process using RF communication.

4.2 Interdisciplinary course

The advanced control systems course was taught in the first semester of 2023, for 10 students, of which five were from the electronic engineering program, four students from the electrical engineering program, and one mechanical engineering student. Students evaluated the course anonymously. Some of the questions related to practical experimentation are shown in Table 1.

Table 2. Questions.

#	Questions
1	The course was relevant to my training.
2	The practice allowed me to develop skills for professional performance.
3	The theoretical knowledge acquired was consistent with the practice I developed.

The questions in Table 2 are rating questions with a range from zero to five, where zero corresponds to the lowest rating and five to the highest. For the questions in Table 1, the students' evaluation of practical experimentation was 5.0/5.0. The overall course average was 4.47/5.0.

With these results it can be concluded that practical experimentation has been well accepted by students, highlighting that it is easy to use, integrates different physical elements and different types of signals in a control loop, of great support for learning control systems. Some observations from the students were that the interdisciplinary course helped them carry out practical experiments based on the theoretical concepts of control systems.

4.3 Project course

At the time of writing, the course is 50% complete; the teachers of the three courses participate in its development. So far, student participation has been very active and purposeful; The evaluation of the first phase of the projects had an average grade of NN. Full results are expected to be reported in a future publication.

5 Conclusions

IoT includes various technologies such as Cloud Computing, Data Analytics, Virtual Reality, and Communications. Engineering education has the challenge of integrating these technologies into its teaching-learning processes, also providing new transversal skills such as problem-solving, systemic analysis, and computational thinking. This work has presented experimental resources in the context of IoT. They allow local real/virtual processes, and local/cloud controllers, interconnected through RF networks or the internet. This allows students to connect to the experimental resource anytime, anywhere. The results of having used these resources in the interdisciplinary course, show good experimental behaviors, relevance in the formation of control systems, and high acceptance by students. The use of these experimental resources in engineering project courses is just beginning, but they already show the advantages of using the IoT as an integrative experimental resource.

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